

“A Study To Asses The Knowledge And Practice Regarding Sleep Hygiene Among Young Adults In Selected Colleges, Thrissur”

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ABSTRACT: Sleep hygiene is a behaviour modification that can improve the fulfillment of sleep needs. This behaviour or habit is very effective in the process of improving the quality, quantity and fulfillment of sleep needs. Lack of knowledge about good sleep hygiene contributes to poor sleep practices, which then affects health and well-being. Taking into consideration, the importance of sleep hygiene and its impact on both physical and mental health, this quantitative study was conducted to assess the knowledge and practice of sleep hygiene among young adults at selected colleges of Thrissur district. The main objectives of the study were to assess the knowledge regarding sleep among young adults, assess the practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults, and correlate the knowledge and practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults through the purposive sampling technique, 60 participants who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were selected as samples. The tools used in the study were The Sleep Hygiene Awareness and Practice Scale (SHAPS) and Sleep Hygiene Index (SHI). The study was conducted in Don Bosco College, Mannuthy, Thrissur. Data collected was analyzed by quantitative and inferential statistics. The study revealed that, out of 60 samples, 35 (58.3%) had good knowledge, 25 (41.7%) had adequate knowledge and none of the sample had poor knowledge regarding sleep hygiene. Sleep hygiene practice was measured using the tool Sleep Hygiene Index (SHI), out of 60 samples, 4 (6.7%) had good practice, 48 (80.0%) had adequate practice, and 8 (13.3%) had poor practice. The present study reveals there is no correlation found between the level of knowledge and practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults with Spearman's correlation coefficient value - .094.

Keywords: *sleep hygiene, young adults, knowledge, practice.*

INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a requirement for normal human functioning, with various functions that contribute to overall physical and mental well-being. It is reasonable to believe that a body requires a tranquil relaxation period to revitalize itself. Experiments in the research milieu subjecting rats show that total sleep deprivation can even lead to death. Some researchers, using an evolutionary perspective, suggest that sleep permitted human ancestors to conserve energy at night, a time when food was relatively hard to come by. Still, this explanation is speculative and although we know that some sleep is necessary, we do not fully know why we must sleep. Sleep health is essential for overall health, quality of life and safety. Researchers have found a reduction in the average hours of sleep among college students. Poor sleep has been associated with deficits in attention, reduction in academic performance, impaired

driving, risk-taking behaviours, depression, impaired social relationships and poorer health. College students may have limited knowledge about sleep hygiene and the behaviours that supports sleep health, which may lead to poor sleep hygiene behaviour. Scientists have been unable to establish just how much sleep is absolutely required. For instance, today most people sleep seven to eight hours a day, but their sleep hours at night are less compared to that of the people who lived a hundred years ago. In addition, there is wide variability among individuals, with some people needing as little as three hours of sleep. Sleep requirements also vary over the course of a lifetime: As they age, people generally need less and less sleep. People who participate in sleep Deprivation experiments, in which they are kept awake for stretches as long as 200 hours, show no lasting effects. It is no fun- they feel weary and irritable, cannot concentrate, and show a decline in logical reasoning ability. However, after being allowed

to sleep normally, they bounce back quickly and are able to perform at pre-deprivation levels after just a few days.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Sleep is important for maintaining a healthy lifestyle. It is a process of relaxing. Deprivation of sleep for several consecutive days can lead to lack of energy, irritability, blurred vision and memory loss. The need for adequate sleep is essential. Sleep is a natural state of rest characterized by altered consciousness and relative inactivity, It is a recurrent, altered state of consciousness that occurs for sustained periods, restoring energy and well-being. Sleep is an active and complex rhythmic state involving the progression of repeated cycles, each representing different phases of body and brain activity. Sleep is a cyclical state of decreased motor activity and perception. Body functions slow and metabolism falls by 20-30%, so the body conserves energy. Sleep leaves them feeling refreshed, rejuvenated, and ready to resume the activities of the day. A person at rest is calm, at ease relaxed, and free of anxiety and stress. People rest by doing things they find relaxing. For example, reading, listening to music, watching television, doing needlework, praying, meditating, gardening, baking, playing golf, walking and camping. Although necessary and beneficial, rest without sleep is inadequate. At rest, the body is disturbed by all external stimuli, whereas at sleep it is screened from them by altered consciousness.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study to assess the knowledge and practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults in selected colleges in Thrissur.

OBJECTIVES

- ❖ To assess the knowledge regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.
- ❖ To assess the reported practice regarding sleep among young adults.
- ❖ To correlate the level of knowledge and practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.

HYPOTHESIS

H1: There is a significant correlation between the knowledge and practice among young adults regarding sleep hygiene.

METHODOLOGY

This study has adopted a quantitative approach to assess the knowledge and practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

The procedure for data collection is the identification of subjects and practices, and systematic gathering of information relevant to the purpose of research. The study was conducted on first year students of BBA department. 60 samples were taken and one and a half hours was the duration for completing the questionnaire. As they were degree students English questionnaire was provided. The researchers obtained permission from the management of Don Bosco College, Thrissur. The data was collected on 16th October 2023. Samples were selected by purposive sampling technique, after obtaining oral consent, and appropriate instructions were given to the samples. After the clarification of doubts, the questionnaire was completed in the presence of the investigators to avoid incompleteness in the collection of data.

RESEARCH DESIGN : In this study descriptive survey design was used.

RESEARCH VARIABLES : The present study aims to assess the knowledge and practice of sleep hygiene among young adults at a selected college in Thrissur. Population: In this study the population selected comprises of students who are in the age group of 19-25 and studying in a selected college, in Thrissur. Target population : it includes students in the age group of 19-25 at Don Bosco College who meet the inclusive criteria.

Accessible population: Accessible Population comprised of students available at Don Bosco college during the time of the study (16th- 18th October 2023).

Sampling Technique: The purposive sampling technique is adopted for this study.

Sample Size : The sample size of the study comprised 60 students of Don Bosco College, Thrissur.

Sample Criteria Inclusion criteria:

- Students who are between the age group of 18-25
- Students who are willing to participate in the study
- Students who are able to read and write English.

Exclusion criteria:

- Students who are not willing to participate in the study
- Students who cannot read and write English.
- Students who are absent on the day of data collection

Description and scoring

SECTION A : Distribution of samples according to socio-demographic variables.

SECTION B : Distribution of samples based on level of knowledge regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.

SECTION C : Distribution of samples based on level of practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.

SECTION D : Analysis and interpretation of the correlation between knowledge and practice of sleep hygiene among young adults.

RESULT FINDINGS:

SECTION A : Distribution of samples according to socio-demographic variables.

SL NO	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Gender		
	a) Male	38	63.3%
	b)Female	22	36.7%
2	Type of family		
	a) Nuclear	56	93.3%
	b)Joint	4	6.7%
3	Intake of medication		
	a)Yes	8	13.3%
	b)No	52	86.7%
4	Part time job		
	a) Yes	9	15.0%
	b)No	51	85.0%
5	Studying other courses		
	a)Yes	2	3.3%
	b)No	58	96.7%
6	Usage of electronic gadgets		
	a)Less than 2 hours	4	6.7%
	b)2-6 hours	43	71.7%
	c)More than 6 hours	13	21.7%
7	Sleeping hours		
	a)Less than 4 hours	3	5.0%
	b)5-7 hours	38	63.3%
	c) 7-9 hours	19	31.7%
8	Knowledge of sleep hygiene		
	a)Yes	42	70.0%
	b)No	18	30.0%

SECTION B : Distribution of samples based on level of knowledge regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.

SL NO	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	FREQUENCY(f)	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	a)Good knowledge	35	58.3%
2	b)Adequate knowledge	25	41.7%
3	c)Poor knowledge	0	0%

SECTION C : Distribution of samples based on level of practice regarding sleep Hygiene among young adults.

SL NO	LEVEL OF PRACTICE	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Good	4	6.7%
2	Adequate	48	80.0%
3	Poor	8	13.3%

SECTION D : Analysis and interpretation of the correlation between knowledge and practice of sleep hygiene among young adults.

VARIABLES	MEAN SCORE	SPEARMAN'S RANK CORRELATION
Knowledge	24.70	-0.094
Practice	24.47	

DISCUSSION

The first objective was to assess the level of knowledge regarding sleep hygiene among young adults in selected colleges in Thrissur:

Regarding the level of knowledge on sleep hygiene among young adults, out of 60 samples, 35 (58.3%) had good knowledge, 25

(41.7%) had adequate knowledge and 0 (0%) had poor knowledge. The mean score for knowledge was 24.70.

The second objective was to assess the practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults in selected colleges in Thrissur:

Concerning the level of practice on sleep hygiene among young adults, out of 60 samples, 4 (6.7%) had good practice, 48 (80%) had adequate practice and 8 (13.3%) had poor practice. The mean score for practice was 24.47.

The third objective was to correlate the knowledge and practice regarding sleep hygiene among young adults:

The relationship between the level of knowledge and practice of sleep hygiene is tested by Spearman's correlation coefficient . There was only a no correlation found between knowledge and practice and the coefficient score for knowledge and practice was - 0.094, which shows that though young adults are aware of sleep hygiene, they are not practicing it.

Conclusion

Sleep hygiene is the set of behavioral and environmental aspects that support healthy sleep patterns. The present study divulges that there is a no correlation found between knowledge and practice. Thus, the finding shows that though young adults have knowledge about sleep hygiene they are not practicing it. Good sleep practices can be maintained by improving attitudes regarding sleep hygiene among young adults.

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